

**Demographic and General Questionnaire: PARKINSON PATIENT:
Measurement Day 1**

Date: _____ Time: _____ Investigator: _____

1. DEMOGRAPHIC PARTICIPANT DATA:

ID:

Gender:

Age:

Ethnicity:

Place of birth:

Highest education level achieved (+ count the years of schooling):

Current Employment Position:

Retirement day (if applicable):

Native language:

Fluently speaking languages:

Partnership status (circle): Married / Extramarital Affair / Single / Widow

Living independently (instead of in a nursing home): Yes / No

Sight (circle): Normal / Corrected to normal

Color vision (circle): OK / Selective blindness, specify:

Handedness:

Experiment experience: Psychology / EEG / EMG / ECG / Eye-tracking / ...

Skin sensitivity: Normal / Skin Allergy / Oversensitive skin

2. PHYSICAL CHARACTERISTICS

Body mass:

Body height:

BMI score:

Leg length:

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3. GENERAL HEALTH DATA

Do you currently have:

CONDITION		Y / N	Onset time	Severity	Drug therapy	Exclusion Y / N
Neurological condition						
Acute head injury						
Diagnosis of a psychiatric condition	depression schizophrenia bipolar disorder other					
Hypertension						
Diabetes (I or II)						
Cardiac conditions						
Neoplasm						
Obesity						
Metabolic condition						
Cerebrovascular disease						
Osteoporosis						
Rheumatological diseases						
Arthrosis						
Other/tremor						

Ongoing drug therapy (other than that against PD). Describe and specify which drug and amount.

Demographic and General Questionnaire: PARKINSON PATIENT: Measurement Day 1

4. MOVEMENT- RELATED QUESTIONS

Do you have any gait-related problems?

History of lower limb injury (fractures, ligament injuries, ...)?

History of lower limb surgery (knee replacement, ...)?

If so, are you still in pain or discomfort because of the lower limb injury/surgery? Please mark where, and how strong: 0 (no pain) – 10 (the worst pain imaginable):

Has the range of motion (ROM) changed because of the injury/surgery?

Do you have any pains or aches unrelated to these injuries/surgeries? If so, please mark these too on the figure below.

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5. OTHER

Do you feel unwell at the moment?

If yes, please state your symptoms: kind (cold, headaches, etc...) duration and intensity:

What did you mostly do during the last hour before coming to us?

How mentally exhausting was the activity for you? [1-not at all, 7-Extremely]

How physically exhausting was the activity for you? [1-not at all, 7-Extremely]

How many hours did you sleep last night? Is this below/above/average?

How much coffee/black tea/energy drinks/coca colas did you have today? Is this below/above/average?

Do you smoke?

How many did you have today? Is this below/above/average?

Have you consumed any alcoholic beverages within the last eight hours?

If yes, please state which, how many, and how long ago.

Have you taken any medicine today?

If yes, please state which, how many, and how long ago.

Have you been taking any drugs within the last 24 hours?

If yes, please state which, how many, and how long ago.

Is there anything else you would like to share with us?

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6. PARKINSON-SPECIFIC DATA, COGNITIVE ASSESSMENT,
QUESTIONNAIRES & TESTS:

Patient's age at Diagnosis:

Patient's age at Parkinson's Disease onset (estimate):

Duration of Diagnosis:

The time between disease onset and the start of the treatment:

Disease Phenotype (circle): Tremor-dominant / Akinetic-Rigid / Mixed

Ongoing PD drug therapy (Describe and specify which drug and amount):

- L-DOPA
- Dopamine Agonists
- L-DOPA + Dopamine Agonists
- Other:

History of PD drug therapy (which drug and amount):

Hahr & Yahr Score:

UPDRS Score:

- I:
- II.
- III.
- IV
- Total:
- FOG score:

MoCA score:

SPPB score:

Falls history:

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FES-I:

Hamilton:

Edenborough Handedness Q.:

TMT-A:

TMT-B: